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PREVALENCE OF EMERGING PATHOGENS IN TICKS REMOVED FROM HUMANS (SERBIA, 2022)

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Introduction: Ticks carry numerous pathogens that, if transmitted, can cause diseases in susceptible humans and animals.

Materials and methods: The One Health study, in addition to the approach to investigate clinical pictures after tick bites, also describes how to investigate the presence of major pathogens in tick samples (n=93) collected from patients (n=83) during 2020. For the detection of pathogens transmitted by ticks, using an unbiased microfluidic Real-Time PCR assay of high throughput.

Results: Ticks species infesting humans were morphologically identified to be four different species including *Ixodes ricinus* (47 females, 34 nymphs, and 6 larvae), *Rhipicephalus sanguineus* sensu lato (2 females and 1 male), *Dermacentor reticulatus* (2 females), and *Haemaphysalis punctata* (1 nymph), which were collected from 81, 3, 2, and 1 patient(s), respectively. PCR-positive results for the presence of TBP were

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detected in *I. ricinus* (70.12%), followed by *R. sanguineus* s.l. (33.33%), and *H. punctata* (100%), while no TBPs were detected in the *D. reticulatus* ticks. DNA Rickettsia spp. was detected in 41/93 (44.09%) tick samples, followed by Anaplasma/Ehrlichia spp. in 19/93 (20.43%), and Borrelia spp. in 18/93 (19.35%), while DNA of protozoan pathogens Babesia/Hepatozoon spp. was detected in 18/93 (19.35%) tick samples. Overall, 16 different pathogens with variable prevalence were identified using species-specific primers. Different Rickettsia species were the most common TBPs identified in the ticks. The presence of TBPs such as *Rickettsia helvetica*, *Rickettsia monacensis*, *Borrelia lusitaniae*, *Borrelia burgdorferi*, *Borrelia afzelii*, *A. phagocytophilum*, and *B. microti* in ticks was further confirmed by DNA sequencing.

Conclusion: The combination of high-throughput screening of TBPs and One Health approaches might help characterize chains of infection leading to human infection by TBPs, as well as prevalence of emerging rickettsial pathogens in the Balkan region.

Keywords: *Microfluidic Real-Time PCR assay, Pathogens, Ticks*